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A Solution to the Dilemma Between R&D Expansion and the Productivity Decline: Lessons from the R&D Models in Amazon and Finland

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Co-Evolutionary Coupling Between Captured and Uncaptured GDP Cycles: Cross Learning from Amazon and Finland Models for Sustainability

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Co-Evolutionary Coupling Via A Digital-Bio Ecosystem – A Suggestion for A New R&D Model in the Digital Economy

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